

REFORMULATION OF THE SPECIAL COMMITTEE FOR TECHNICAL EVALUATION OF MEDICAL AND HOSPITAL ITEMS

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ABSTRACT

Demands for materials emerge from the “Health Sector”, which can impact diagnosis, disease progression, lack of treatment and even loss of life. In the search for an effective tool for qualified purchasing, reducing risks, the proposal for pre-qualification of hospital products emerged. This is a descriptive study on the implementation of new routines and work processes for the evaluation and acquisition of medical-hospital articles at INCA. A quantitative survey of cases that passed through CEAT between 2019 and 2021 was carried out. The number of cases processed decreases over the periods, leaving a total of 5,409 cases in the first year to 2,142 in the second year of the evaluated period. The time taken to complete the material purchase processes was reduced from 89 to 14 days in the period. Meanwhile, the brand prequalification processes decreased from 90 to 22 days. Facts that corroborate the effectiveness of the service performed by CEAT during this composition. These results reflect the contribution of professionals who dedicated themselves to the non-interruption of care and maintenance of quality patient care.

Keywords: Prequalification, medical-hospital articles, processes.

INTRODUCTION

The National Cancer Institute (INCA) is an entity of the Ministry of Health (MS), directly linked to the Secretariat of Specialized Health Care (SAES), and its relevance to the Unified Health System (SUS) is described in the Organic Law itself. of SUS – Law nº 8,080/1990, art. 41 – which highlighted INCA as a “reference for service provision, human resource training and technology transfer” in the area of Oncology (BRASIL, 2020). It is also a High Complexity Assistance Center in Oncology (Cacon), according to SAS/MS Ordinance No. 140/2014, working in the formulation of the National Policy for Cancer Prevention, Diagnosis and Treatment. The Institute's mission is: “to promote cancer control with integrated national actions in prevention, assistance, teaching and research”. And its vision consists of: “fully exercising its governmental role as an Integrated Center, of national and international reference, for oncological care, teaching and research, with excellence in the development of public policies for the prevention and control of cancer, contributing to the well-being of society”. Both are supported by the following values: Ethics and Transparency ; Valuing professionals ; Humanization and Integrality ; Respect ; Social and environmental responsibility ; Equity ; Innovation ; Excellence (BRAZIL, 2020) .

Within the scope of Public Health, healthcare establishments must be deeply committed to quality. In this sense, Public Administration has an essential role in making this possible, and it is up to it to manage efficiently and effectively, being responsible and without procedural delays, constituting one of the most difficult challenges for its managers. “Health” is a fundamental sector in a society, from which procedural demands emerge for the purchase of materials, which can often result in difficulty in diagnosis, progression of the disease, lack of treatment and even loss of life. In this context, the acquisition of hospital medical items requires speed and quality as a requirement for safe care. A methodology must be created that allows the evaluation of medical and hospital products in the pre-acquisition phase, through flows and procedures to validate regularity and quality for each product category.

In the search for an effective tool for risk management, based on monitoring and consulting health alerts in order to identify possible risks or those already identified in similar articles, the proposal for pre-qualification of medical and hospital articles emerged. This pre-qualification aims to assist in the selection of the most suitable items/products for acquisition and use, providing better and greater protection for users and patients. It comprises a process that includes obtaining a series of information and carrying out legal, technical and functional assessments before making a purchasing decision. The technical specification of articles before

their acquisition minimizes problems arising from this product not complying with the specificities of the procedure in which it will be used.

With the aim of ensuring the safety of patients and professionals at this Institution with articles that meet the specificities inherent to its activity and, concomitantly, subsidize its actions in Law No. 8,666/93, mainly in its article 3, “not restricting the participation of suppliers whose brands were approved by Anvisa” (BRASIL, 1993). At the end of 2005, Inca submitted process 25410.001884/2005-31 to the Federal Attorney General's Office (AGU) and to the Legal Consultancy of the Ministry of Health, process 25410.001884/2005-31, with a proposal for a pre-payment system. -qualification of products for participation in bidding competitions at the Institute. Thus limiting the participation in bidding processes of materials previously tested and approved by users/employees according to the need and specificity of the clinical characteristics of users/patients of a High Complexity Oncological Institution such as INCA.

In this context, the Special Commission for Technical Assessment of Medical and Hospital Articles (CEAT) was formalized in March 2006, subordinate to INCA's Assistance Coordination (COAS), aiming mainly to ensure quality standards for patient care, carrying out pre-qualification of materials as conduct and part of your work process.

A robust computerized database was then created containing a list of approved brands for each item specifically, as well as those that had previously proven an occurrence that did not allow its use at Inca. Supplier companies previously presented their materials for testing, accompanied by the minimum required supporting documents relating to the product and the company. The procedure always follows the criteria of Law No. 9,784/99, which “regulates the administrative process within the scope of the Federal Public Administration” (BRASIL, 1999). The prerequisites and rules for presenting are always available in publications on the Inca website, and currently, administrative processes can be monitored through the Electronic Information System (SEI). Administrative proceedings may also be opened to investigate negative events with materials already approved, which after due analysis may lead to the disqualification of the brand and the communication of the fact to ANVISA. This practice has its legal support approved in 6 de maio de 2006, when they were approved by a committee of Union lawyers and ratified by the Legal Consultancy of the Ministry of Health (BRAZIL, 1999).

The acquisition of articles without careful quality analysis, for use in health units, may result in the occurrence of undesirable events affecting the health condition of patients, exposure of occupational risks to health professionals, in addition to being able to result in a waste of financial resources invested in the purchasing products that do not meet their intended purpose. It is important to highlight that medical-hospital items represent half of the products

used in clinical procedures and that the acquisition of low-quality inputs increases the working hours of health professionals, with a consequent negative impact on the quality of patient care. In addition to increased professional stress, increased material expenditure to achieve the same purpose, failure to achieve the expected result with a product of reduced quality, among others (ANVISA, 2008).

Pre-qualification and periodic review of products aim to ensure a better quality of assistance provided, also protecting the professional in terms of worker health and the institution as an efficient management, with a lower rate of wasted working hours in the administrative sphere. This process consists of steps involving in-depth and complex information gathering and enabling technical, legal, health and functional analyses, including user testing. It must be suitable, impartial, robust, with a technical foundation characterized by the smoothness of the process from start to finish.

It is of fundamental importance to form a *Commission* for the Assessment of hospital medical products in each institution and that they have professionals with knowledge of these articles in the specific area of their application in health care. During the legal, technical and functional evaluation of the article, which will qualify the health articles for use, the Legislation recommended by the Federal Government, Ministry of Health, National Health Surveillance Agency and Consumer Protection Code_Law 8,078 of 11 must be respected /09/90 (BRAZIL, 1990). This includes the presentation by suppliers of article registrations at ANVISA, in accordance with RDC No. 185/2001 of ANVISA/MS, with its publication in the DOU or the registration document (RDC 260/02) of the products, in applicable cases. . This technical support structure must research antecedents of adverse events associated with articles in the risk management, NOTIVISA and Technovigilance Alerts databases (ANVISA , 2008).

Based on the verification of compliance of the product(s) with health legislation and resolutions recommended by ANVISA on labeling and packaging, the Commission can, internally, create a method of evaluating these articles together with professional users in the care areas . The first step of this method should consist of developing article evaluation sheets, or forms that contain specific technical criteria for each product or class of articles, and the logistics of forwarding the articles to professional users, together with due guidance on the characteristics and the parameters to be evaluated. This referral also records the number of samples to be tested as well as the deadlines within which the evaluations must be carried out. In the case of articles with specific characteristics that require training, the technical area requests the presence of the supplier company's technical representative for the presentation and/or demonstration and schedules training with professionals/users.

Before the opening of the bidding process for the acquisition of medical and hospital products and upon the existence of a specific Commission in the Institution, only supplier companies that have their articles pre-qualified in accordance with the methodology followed by the Institution, as well as the established deadline, can participate. in Notice. Companies that supply items not previously qualified or disqualified from the list of positively evaluated brands do not participate in the auction (ANVISA , 2008) .

Conversation, harmony and integration between the work processes of different sectors of the institution are of fundamental importance for the process of acquiring medical-hospital materials: Special Commission for Technical Assessment of Medical-Hospital Articles (CEAT), Supply Division (DISUP), Technical Advisory (ASTECH), Bidding Processes Committee (CPL), Purchasing Service (SECOM), areas using materials, CCIH, Technovigilance, among others. The pre-qualification process is not static, but is constantly evolving and improving, and can establish close relationships with new departments to improve the quality of the process.

Health services base their material pre-qualification work process on some fundamental pillars, which are basically: compliance with legal requirements by the company and its product in question, compliance with the institution's material specification in line with the demands of the health service ,functional evaluation by relevant user. Simply complying with the “lowest price” prerogative will not always be more advantageous for the Public Administration. Therefore, in this scenario, the pre-qualification process is so important, as it aims to ensure minimum standards of adequacy and quality of medical-hospital materials for the institution.

In 2017, the members working on the Commission were already reporting the difficulties encountered in carrying out a good job, such as the lack of a team of employees dedicated exclusively to working in this group. Given the need for greater organization of processes, with large demands for purchasing materials, the need for pre-qualification of new brands and review of brands, previously pre-qualified, that have not been used in recent years or that have had any change in the composition of the product or the manufacturer, INCA's Assistance Coordination (COAS) organized a reformulation of CEAT, aiming to restructure the service, redesign flows and review demands that could improve and speed up the completion of administrative processes.

Therefore, this study aimed to analyze whether the restructuring of CEAT, with the implementation of new routines and work processes, achieved the objectives expected by the institution, providing greater speed and procedural quality for the acquisition of medical and hospital articles.

METHODS

This is a descriptive study on the restructuring of INCA's CEAT with the implementation of new routines and work processes for the evaluation and acquisition of medical and hospital articles for the institution. A retrospective evaluation was carried out of the results obtained from the new configuration of this Commission established by INCA Ordinance No. 747, of September 24, 2019, which was the first team with members exercising their full workload for this purpose (INCA, 2021).

The object of this survey were processes that depended on CEAT's tasks, such as, for example, carrying out documentary analysis, user reports and issuing opinions requesting the inclusion of a new brand as pre-qualified and reviewing documentation of brands that had previously qualified for checking the validity of documentation. Therefore, as can be seen in the procedural workflow, the results of this Commission directly interfere, positively or negatively, in the purchasing processes of hospital materials for all units that make up INCA, with a direct impact on the care of patients served by the hospital.

A quantitative survey was carried out on the number of processes that passed through CEAT in the period from October 2019 to November 2021. These processes were divided as completed or in progress and the review of pre-qualified brands and the evaluation of new brands to be qualified after user analysis. All data were taken from the programs used for the Commission's work, such as the SEI (Electronic Information System) available for all Federal units. As there was no participation of Human Beings in the research as it was exclusively electronic data, it was not necessary to use a free and informed consent form (TCLE) and/or approval by the Ethics Committee. The data were calculated using the Microsoft Excel[®] 2007 program and described as whole numbers, in order to show the team's performance during the studied period.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

Pre-qualification aims to select safe materials that are most suitable for the purposes and realities existing within the institution. This scenario must consider the profile of the professionals who will use the material, the work methodology and the individuality of the patient (their needs, characteristics, age, among others), the different sectors of care users present within the institution. In September 2019, CEAT followed the internal regulations drawn up in May 2016 and had a work proposal based on the technical evaluation of the product

and health documentation after opening the pre-qualification process, followed by a technical opinion with the result of the post-test report and decision to qualify positively or negatively and, subsequently, the request for inclusion or not in the catalog of pre-qualified Brands.

Furtado and Geron (2020) understand that the absence of a process map or flowchart constitutes one of the biggest managerial and operational pitfalls of the cycle as a whole; which leads to weaknesses and the lack of a complete and global view of the processes and their interrelationships. Updating and re-analyzing the flowchart allows you to eliminate unnecessary steps, change their sequence, introduce new ones, integrate them, adapt interfaces, streamline processes, and parallelize them with other important activities (FURTADO; GERON, 2020).

Thus, during the transition, the former team began preparing the review process for the institution's existing pre-qualification processes. Many were out of date with the new technologies launched on the market, dynamisms and mergers in the commercial market and, some perhaps presented procedural defects that had previously been identified, which needed to adapt to the new requirements of the controlling bodies. The information flow of the pre-qualification process had a well-structured skeleton, as long as it no longer included certain peculiar situations that the new team began to experience. As the team encountered particularities, new alignments were discussed and carried out, always aiming for the final objective established with the implemented changes.

Failure to establish definitions and designs makes the management and traceability of actions difficult, as well as the occurrence of events that generate consecutive rework. Actions arising from non-standardized specific requests in the flow can generate duplicate controls, making the process time-consuming and management much more complex and difficult to execute (ABPMP, 2013).

As for the index of sample qualification processes, it is made up of pre-qualification and review processes. Pre-qualification processes are initiated when interested suppliers present themselves to the institution, with the aim of submitting a product from a certain *brand* to the institute's evaluation screen with a view to qualifying for participation in future bidding processes. For each product itself, a pre-qualification process is opened or the appropriate review is carried out, thus justifying the much higher number of sample qualification processes when compared to purchasing processes. A list of items are included in the same purchasing process, which also explains their smaller number relative to sample qualifications.

The documentary analysis of the pre-qualification process is made up of two variables: administrative/fiscal and health regularity. With regard to administrative regularity, the CNPJ is consulted on the Federal Revenue website in order to check whether the company is Active

or Inactive; and whether the related activities are in accordance with its function and proposal. The municipal operating certificate is also evaluated. Regarding sanitary items, the situation regarding ANVISA Registration, ANVISA Instruction for Use, ANVISA Labeling, Company Operating License at ANVISA, ANVISA Technical Documentation, consultation of publications in the Official Gazette of the Union (DOU) are assessed. The technical analysis consists of visual inspection of the product and its adaptation to the institutional narrative, in addition to consulting such documents on the ANVISA website, searches on the website of the Manufacturer and/or Import Holder in the country and consultation of the Manufacturer/ Holder Virtual Catalog / Supplier.

The structuring of the administrative pre-qualification process in the SEI system follows the following order: Request from the interested company; Documentary Attachment; Receipt of Documentation and Samples; Pre-qualified Trademark Request; Material Coding Documentation; Movement of item stock in the institution; Order from Technical Advisory (ASTEC/DISUP) forwarding for evaluation by the technical team; Technical Assessment Order; Evaluated documents are attached to the process tree; User's Technical Report and Technical Opinion prepared by the technical evaluation team.

The planning of the administrative purchasing process must contain information such as a study with the institution's expected annual consumption, breakdown of the amount intended to be purchased, conditions for purchasing materials. The term of reference must contain the product specification, contracting grounds and requirements, contract management model, measurement and payment criteria, budget adequacy, indication of delivery locations and rules for receiving inputs and materials as well as the preliminary project and basic project (Law 14,133/2021).

Pre-qualification according to Law 13,303/2016 (“State-Owned Companies Law” - LLE) and Law 14,133/2021 (“Law on Tenders and Administrative Contracts” - LLC) constitutes an auxiliary procedure for public bidding. It is also an administrative process (art.80 of the LLC), which may describe any object, as long as the minimum information for future bids is disclosed (BRASIL, 2016 and 2021) .

The number of processes processed decreases over the periods (figure 1), going from a total of 5,409 processes in the first year to 2,142 in the second year of the evaluated period. Because, as the team's work unfolded and evolved, it became possible to overcome the backlog of processes in the sector. Until we can reach the current moment, in which we process the processes according to the demands of new pre-qualifications established and a few remaining revisions. According to Lima (2019) , the performance of public servants and the way of organizing and structuring managerial and operational dynamics are related to the principle of efficiency.

In figure 2, the much higher numbers of sample qualification processes (5,405) are justified when compared to purchasing processes (294), because as previously described, for each product itself, a certain corresponding brand/reference is One (01) pre-qualification process was initiated and processed. For example: even if a supplier company has the same type, brand and line of catheters, it is necessary to open a sample qualification process for each specific caliber. This flow is necessary, as public purchases can cover a certain caliber of catheter, and do not need to purchase another size. In this example, this phenomenon may be due to having a different catheter size still in stock, or not being used in the institution. A similar phenomenon extends to a multitude of hospital supplies.

In the institutional dynamics currently in force, it is important to highlight that the qualification of brands, as well as their related suppliers, allows distributors to align and document conferences in advance; that is, without linking to a specific purchasing process or any guarantees of future contracting. In this model, *brands/references* that have qualified suppliers form a base capable of participating in bidding processes, according to the institution's demands. It is worth noting that after positive pre-qualification of a specific *brand/reference*, any distributor offering such input (same *brand/reference*) can apply to participate in the institution's bidding processes. The legality of these suppliers' documentation will be checked during the bidding process by the appropriate team responsible for the Tenders sector.

With regard to the graph in figure 3 (Documents generated in each period), the high number of dispatches (5,449) is due to the fact that it is a type of document prepared in all types of processes processed in the sector and evaluated by the team technique. Whether they are pre-qualification or review, regardless of the result, whether pre-qualified positively, negatively,

maintaining the brand in the institutional catalog or excluding it (these last two specifically refer to review processes). This significant result can also be explained because, regardless of the content of the decision, orders need to be generated. Whether they are: pre-qualified brand conformity analysis (*positive* – proceeding to testing) (*negative* – process closure), brand review conformity analysis (*sent to the user for approval*), or closure (*non-adaptation* or withdrawal of the brand – possible examples: irregular health document, product has had its technology modified, reference change, material is no longer manufactured, among others). Other types of orders can be prepared, such as: analysis of pre-qualified brand compliance (*pending issues* - request for a document that may be missing from the documentation and requests for clarification) and response to appeals, be they: questioning companies regarding the result of a technical opinion (*approval* or *rejection*) or clarification of doubts from the bidding support service/auctioneer.

According to Freire, pre-qualification constitutes a sequence of “legal acts and facts that aim at a final result: the administrative act of pre-qualification.” In light of the law on administrative proceedings within the scope of the Federal Public Administration (Law 9,784/1999), the right to adversarial proceedings and full defense for interested parties is guaranteed. (BRAZIL, 1999 and 2021).

Furthermore, according to the graph in figure 3, number of emails, these only express emails sent within the SEI system. It does not cover emails sent via the sector/team email box, which we emphasize that the vast majority were sent outside the system. Therefore, this number is much smaller than the real number, compared to the total number of emails (via SEI and those in the email box, which cannot be counted).

As for the number of technical opinions (2,785), these rates are much lower when compared to the number of dispatches. Therefore, for each decision-making stage of the technical assessment team and/or phase of the process, an order is generated, with only one (01) technical opinion being issued in each pre-qualification process. Some processes end before the technical opinion preparation stage. The processes that were previously closed, in general, are due to “ *non-conformity*” in the analysis and thus did not continue and go through the entire flow dynamics.

The notes correspond to small additions of important details to the process, when perhaps forgotten or mistaken in dispatch.

As for external documents generated in each period (figure 4), the attached files present significant numbers, as they refer to all technical and health documents consulted in order to support the analysis of the technical assessment. The tiny number of reports is justified, as the majority of these documents were attached by the technical assistance department of the supply division (DISUP), and were not accounted for and recorded in the information system of this team (technical evaluation sector). The number of technical opinions issued does not correspond to the above, as it is not recorded in the SEI system as an external document.

The new Law 14,133 of 2021 establishes and updates the new guidelines and rules regarding Tenders and Administrative Contracts (BRAZIL, 2021). The bidding modality practiced by the institution is the *auction*, concomitantly with *pre-qualification*, which is considered as one of the possible auxiliary procedures according to legislation. In the aforementioned Law, in its section III, article 80, pre-qualification is conceptualized or defined as an administrative procedure, however of an extremely technical nature. (BRAZIL, 2021). The purpose of which is to select bidders in advance, that is, interested companies that meet the minimum conditions, both qualification (characterization and specificity) and legal, to participate in future auctions; as well as the goods, which constitute hospital inputs that must meet the technical characteristics pre-established by the institution. Such technical characteristics aim to meet minimum quality criteria, which are objectively defined through an institutional narrative. At the same time as it meets technical requirements, it is broad (generic) aiming at the impartiality and transparency of Public Administration (BRASIL, 2021). This description is prepared by users, that is, by the specialized services that make up this institute. Each specific material has its narrative suggested by the corresponding specialized service,

which has the expertise for such activity and evaluation of the materials submitted to the pre-qualification screening.

At the same time, the Technical Assessment Committee/Body corroborates the review of the descriptions, preserving transparency, conciseness and compliance with objectively defined criteria, not considering subjective aspects. Enables the pre-qualification of the largest number of brands possible, contributing to the principles of competitiveness, equality, impersonality, reasonableness, objective judgment, economy and public interest, but without neglecting the quality of the items (BRAZIL, 2016; 2020 and 2021).

According to Colombo (2016), the pre-qualification procedure also presents benefits to the Public Administration: minimizing the occurrence of failed items in the auction; greater precision when researching prices to define the bidding reference value, and prior elimination of materials with unwanted quality that, without pre-qualification in a bidding process, would have to be subjected to analysis, delaying the conclusion of the competition.

Thus, by carrying out trials and tests on samples acquired or received from interested parties (manufacturers, commercial representatives, distributors), respecting the principles of equality, publicity, broad defense and contradictory; it is possible to establish a minimum standard of acceptable performance and quality. From this it becomes feasible to research the market in order to identify brands that serve it for the purpose of guiding future acquisitions (CHAVES, 2015).

With CEAT's work on its new formulation, the time taken to complete material purchasing processes reduced from 89 days in October 2019 to 14 days in September 2021. Meanwhile, brand pre-qualification processes decreased from 90 days in October 2019 to 22 days in September 2021. Facts that corroborate the effectiveness of the service provided by this Commission during the period studied. In 2018, the time elapsed during the pre-qualification process was already highlighted by Santos and Daher (2018) as a “great challenge to be overcome”, as it took 108 days to complete.

CONCLUSION

The appropriate approval of brands/references is an advantageous and efficient tool for the Institution and, by extension, the Public Administration. Its adoption allowed greater efficiency in public purchasing, improvement in the supply chain and patient care.

The restructuring of the team with exclusive dedication to this purpose, as well as the reorganization of the work process and relationship-integration between the technical advisory

sectors, supply division and users generated significant advances, until then hampered by the deficit regarding the alignment of the functional vision in a broad way. During the period evaluated, it was possible to obtain greater procedural speed, without neglecting the care for the quality and functioning of public machinery.

There are still problems and certain obstacles in the pre-qualification workflow. For example: the occurrence of procedural delays, often due to the user's delay in returning the technical report; non-compliance or delay in completing outstanding documentation by companies; restriction of team access to some Technical Standards of the Brazilian Association of Technical Standards (ABNT). We identified a gap regarding the institution's lack of incentives for continuous improvement and updating of the technical advisory team. As a technical team, we mobilize to participate more in conferences and *stricto sensu* postgraduate courses.

The measured and tangible results were possible thanks to the awareness and contribution of the institute's management, as well as the divisions, user sectors and especially the professionals, who tirelessly dedicated themselves to ensuring non-interruption of care and maintaining quality patient care. We understand that the actions and flows carried out need to be reviewed frequently, inclined towards innovations aimed at adjustments and updates contributing to the redesign, establishment of routines for continuous improvement of the pre-qualification process in the institution.

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